

Synthesis and Biological Activity of some New Azitidinones and Bicyclic Pyrazoles

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PYRAZOLES and many pyrazole various biological activities¹. Earlier study indicates that incorporation of azitidinone enhances the biological activity². Recently, Fahmy *et al.*³ reported synthesis of some new pyrazolines. These reports prompted us to undertake the preparation of a number of fused pyrazoles and evaluation of their biological activity.

The desired ethyl butyrate 2-arylohydrazones (1) were prepared by the interaction of acetoacetic ester with various substituted arylohydrazines (Scheme 1). The hydrazones (1) undergo cyclocondensation with chloroacetyl chloride in presence of triethylamine to furnish the corresponding β -lactam (2), $\nu_{\max}$ 1590 (C=O monocyclic β -lactam) and 1970 cm^{-1} (C=O amido). Compound 2 undergoes cyclocondensation while refluxing in presence of *o*-dichlorobenzene and gave the corresponding fused bicyclic pyrazoles (3). The disappearance of signals due to ester group in the pmr spectrum indicated the cyclisation.

Scheme 1

Biological activity: All the bicyclic pyrazoles (2) were tested for their antibacterial activity using cup-plate agar diffusion technique⁴ against gram-positive *S. aureus* and gram-negative *E. coli* at 25 and 50 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ concentrations using tetracyclin as a standard.

The azitidinones (2) and bicyclic pyrazoles (3) were also tested for their antifungal activity against *Aspergillus niger* by usual agar-plate method with Blitox 50 WP as a standard at 1000 ppm concentration. In general, bicyclic pyrazoles (3) were found to be relatively more potent than the corresponding azitidinones (2).

Experimental

Melting points were determined by open capillary method and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer and nmr spectra (TFA) on a Perkin-Elmer R-32 instrument using TMS as an internal reference. Homogeneity of the compounds were checked by tlc on silica gel-G plates using iodine as chromogen.

The following procedure forms a general method for the synthesis of compounds 1-3 (Table 1).

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF AZITIDINONES (2)* AND BICYCLIC PYRAZOLES (3)*

Compd. no.	R	Mol. formula	M.p. °C
2a	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ O ₄ N ₂ Cl	220
2b	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ O.C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₁ H ₁₂ O ₄ N ₂ Cl	170
2c	C ₆ H ₅	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ O ₄ N ₂ Cl	115
2d	<i>o</i> -OH.C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₅ N ₂ Cl	160
2e	3,4-(NO ₂) ₂ .C ₆ H ₃ .O.CH ₃	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₅ N ₂ Cl	69
2f	C ₆ H ₅ .OH	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ O ₄ N ₂ Cl	80
2g	3,5-(NO ₂) ₂ .C ₆ H ₃	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ O ₄ N ₂ Cl	95
2h	<i>o</i> -NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄ .O.CH ₃	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₅ N ₂ Cl	240
2i	<i>o</i> -Cl.C ₆ H ₄ .O.CH ₃	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ O ₄ N ₂ Cl	175
2j	C ₆ H ₅ .O.CH ₃	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ O ₄ N ₂ Cl	90
2k	2,4-(OH) ₂ .C ₆ H ₃ .O.CH ₃	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₅ N ₂ Cl	77
2l	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄ .O.CH ₃	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ O ₄ N ₂ Cl	185
2m	<i>o</i> -Cl.C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ O ₄ N ₂ Cl	82
2n	<i>p</i> -Cl. <i>m</i> -OH. C ₆ H ₃ .O.CH ₃	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ O ₅ N ₂ Cl	140
2o	<i>p</i> -Cl.C ₆ H ₄ .O.CH ₃	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ O ₄ N ₂ Cl	90
2p	<i>m</i> -OH.C ₆ H ₄ .O.CH ₃	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₅ N ₂ Cl	60
2q	C ₆ H ₅ .OH=OH	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₄ N ₂ Cl	65
3a	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ O ₄ N ₂ Cl	158
3b	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ O.C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₁ H ₁₂ O ₄ N ₂ Cl	229
3c	C ₆ H ₅	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ O ₄ N ₂ Cl	230
3d	<i>o</i> -OH.C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₅ N ₂ Cl	180
3e	3,4-(NO ₂) ₂ .C ₆ H ₃ .O.CH ₃	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₅ N ₂ Cl	110
3f	C ₆ H ₅ .OH	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ O ₄ N ₂ Cl	70
3g	3,5-(NO ₂) ₂ .C ₆ H ₃	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ O ₄ N ₂ Cl	135
3h	<i>o</i> -NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄ .O.CH ₃	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₅ N ₂ Cl	220
3i	<i>o</i> -Cl.C ₆ H ₄ .O.CH ₃	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ O ₄ N ₂ Cl	162
3j	C ₆ H ₅ .O.CH ₃	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ O ₄ N ₂ Cl	140
3k	2,4-(OH) ₂ .C ₆ H ₃ .O.CH ₃	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₅ N ₂ Cl	155
3l	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄ .O.CH ₃	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ O ₄ N ₂ Cl	105
3m	<i>o</i> -Cl.C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ O ₄ N ₂ Cl	190
3n	<i>p</i> -Cl. <i>m</i> -OH. C ₆ H ₃ .O.CH ₃	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ O ₅ N ₂ Cl	155
3o	<i>p</i> -Cl.C ₆ H ₄ .O.CH ₃	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ O ₄ N ₂ Cl	75
3p	<i>m</i> -OH.C ₆ H ₄ .O.CH ₃	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₅ N ₂ Cl	105

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

Ethyl butyrate-2-arylohydrazones (1): To a solution of the arylohydrazine (1.95 g, 0.01 mol) in dioxane (20 ml) ethyl acetoacetate (0.65 g, 0.005 mol) was added and the mixture was refluxed gently for 4 h. The solvent was then removed under reduced pressure and the residue poured into ice-cold water. The resulting solid was recrystallised

from ethanol to furnish 1a (85%), m.p. 110°; $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1700 (C=O ester), 1600 (C=N) and 1050 cm^{-1} (C-O-C); δ 1.19 (3H, t, CH_3 ester), 2.15 (3H, s, N=C- CH_3), 3.5 (2H, s, CH_2CO), 4.2 (2H, q, CH_2 ester), 6.8-7.5 (4H, m, ArH) and 8.2 (1H, s, CONH exchangeable with D_2O).

1-Substituted-benzamidyl|aryloxamidyl-3-chloro-4-carboethoxymethylmethyl-2-aztidinone (2): To a solution of 1a (3.23 g, 0.01 mol) and triethylamine (0.02 mol) in dioxane (20 ml) was added chloroacetyl chloride (0.02 mol) dropwise with stirring in cold at room temperature. The reaction mixture was stirred for 30 min and then refluxed for 3 h. On cooling, the resulting solid was removed by filtration and the filtrate triturated with ether-petroleum ether (1:1) until it solidified. The solid was recrystallised from a mixture of ethanol and water to give 2a (75%), m.p. 220°; $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3300-3200 (NH), 1720 (C=O ester) and 1660 cm^{-1} (CONH); δ 1.1 (3H, s, CH_3), 1.3 (3H, t, CH_3 ester), 3.5 (2H, s, CH_2CO), 4.2 (2H, q, CH_2 ester), 5.6 (1H, s, CHCl), 7.4-7.5 (2H, d, J_{ortho} 9 Hz, C_6 -H and C_5 -H) and 7.6-7.7 (2H, d, J_{ortho} 9 Hz, C_6 -H and C_5 -H)

N_3 -Substituted-1,2-diazo-4-chloro-5-methyl-3,7-dioxobicyclo[3,2,0]heptane: A solution of 2a (3.69 g, 0.01 mol) was refluxed in *o*-dichlorobenzene (20 ml) for about 5 h and then left overnight. The resulting solid was filtered and recrystallised from ethanol to yield 3a (74%), m.p. 158°; $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1660 (CONH) and 1600 cm^{-1} (C=C); δ 1.1 (3H, s, CH_3), 2.5 (2H, s, CH_2CO), 5.5 (1H, s, CHCl), 7.3-7.4 (2H, d, J 9 Hz, C_6 -H and C_5 -H) and 7.6-7.7 (2H, d, J 9 Hz, C_6 -H and C_5 -H).

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Synthesis of 4-(5-Substituted-arylidine-4-thiazolidinone-2-thione)-6,8-substituted-quinazolines as Potential Anthelmintic Agents

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A series of substituted-quinazolines have been synthesised and found to exhibit anthelmintic activity against *Hymenolepis nana* in rats.

Several compounds containing quinazolone nucleus have recently been introduced for the treatment of infection caused by different intestinal nematodes and cestodes¹. Many 4-thiazolidinone-2-thiones² have been reported to possess broad spectrum of anthelmintic activity. Hence an attempt has been made to synthesise such compounds having both the moieties. The present communication describes the synthesis of 4-(5-substituted-arylidine-4-thiazolidinone-2-thione)-6,8-substituted-quinazolines (3) and their anthelmintic activity. In general, 6,8-substituted-4-chloroquinazolones (1) were prepared by 6,8-substituted-4-quinazolones in presence of PCl_5 and POCl_3 under anhydrous conditions and the intermediate 5-substituted-arylidine-4-thiazolidinone-2-thiones³ (2) were synthesised by refluxing substituted-aldehydes and rhodanines in glacial acetic acid with fused sodium acetate. Condensation of the intermediates 1 and 2 in pyridine gave μ -4-(5-substituted-arylidine-4-thiazolidinone-2-thione)-6,8-substituted-quinazolines.

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillaries and are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 157 spectrophotometer and pmr spectra (CDCl_3 + DMSO-d_6) on a Varian EM 360 instrument.

4-[5-(3,4-Dimethoxy)arylidine-4-thiazolidinone-2-thione]-6-bromoquinazolinone (3): A mixture of 5-